

Yashil IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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- 08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
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RECREATIONAL POTENTIAL OF UZBEKISTAN AND PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF WELLNESS TOURISM IN THE COUNTRY

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Abstract: This article analyses the recreational potential of Uzbekistan. The concepts of medical tourism and wellness tourism have been studied. The results of the Social Survey conducted on the topic were analyzed. Proposals and recommendations for the further development of medical-health tourism in the country have been made.

Key words: recreation, medical tourism, wellness tourism, tourism resources, health tourism, leisure tourism, social survey.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada O'zbekistonning turizm salohiyati tahlil qilinadi. Tibbiyot turizmi va sog'lomlashtirish turizmi tushunchalari o'rganildi. Mavzu bo'yicha o'tkazilgan ijtimoiy so'rov natijalari tahlil qilindi. Mamlakatimizda tibbiy-sog'lomlashtirish turizmini yanada rivojlantirish bo'yicha taklif va tavsiyalar bildirildi.

Kalit so'zlar: dam olish, tibbiy turizm, turizm, turizm resurslari, sog'lomlashtirish turizmi, dam olish turizmi, ijtimoiy so'rov.

Аннотация: В данной статье анализируется рекреационный потенциал Узбекистана. Изучены понятия медицинского туризма и оздоровительного туризма. Проанализированы результаты социального опроса, проведенного по данной теме. Сделаны предложения и рекомендации по дальнейшему развитию лечебно-оздоровительного туризма в стране.

Ключевые слова: рекреация, медицинский туризм, оздоровительный туризм, туристические ресурсы, оздоровительный туризм, развлекательный туризм, социальный опрос.

INTRODUCTION

The field of tourism in Uzbekistan is distinguished by its wide potential and, even though it is young compared to other developing fields, it is making significant progress. Our country is a region where almost all types of tourism can be developed due to the abundance of tourist resources. The uniqueness of the climate and the beautiful nature provide ample opportunities for the development of one of the most important areas of tourism in the country - recreation tourism. Recreational tourism differs from other types of tourism in that it has health benefits.

The attention and legal support given by our state create conditions for the further development of health tourism. It is worth noting that the health of the nation is formed by the health of each person, which is characterized by working ability and an active lifestyle. Thus, people's physical and mental health is a priority strategic monitoring object for the state. The overall health of the nation directly affects the economic and political situation in the country, as well as the development of the state in general.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The importance of health tourism is that it is the most effective means of strengthening the body, recreation, and physical and mental strength. Although medical and wellness tourism is one common concept, the tasks of medical tourism and wellness tourism are separate. According to the definition given by the Medical Tourism Association, "Medical tourism is the travel of people living in one country to another country to receive medical, dental and surgical care. At the same time, they receive care equal to or better than the medical treat-

ment in their home country. “Domestic medical tourism” is when people living in one country travel to another city, region, or state to receive medical, dental, or surgical care while receiving the same, or more, access to health care than they would in their home city. improve, or travel for medical care because of the high level of quality of medical care.” [1]

Medical tourism specialist Dr According to the definition given by Prem Jagyi: “Medical tourism is the travel of people, often over long distances or across borders, for the direct or indirect use of medical services for leisure, business or other purposes. is a complex of trips.” [2]

Health tourism was promoted by Dr P. Jagyasi: “Wellness tourism is the process by which a traveller pursues a special trip to improve or promote their health and well-being. Tourists stay at a destination where they are offered a variety of healthful physical activities, recreational activities and a full range of nutritious food. As more and more people actively seek to improve their health, the health tourism industry has seen rapid growth.” [3]

Summarizing the above points, medical and health tourism can be defined as follows: both of these types of tourism offer health care solutions. Wellness tourism can serve as a continuation of medical tourism after a complete recovery has occurred.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Scientific works of scientists were studied in the research work. The recreational potential of Uzbekistan was analyzed. The population’s needs for recreation were studied with the help of a questionnaire.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The wealth of recreational resources such as the beautiful landscape, unique and magnificent mountains, beautiful and charming waterfalls, and climate of our country makes this place extremely attractive and allows for the development of any type of tourism. The presence of recreation centres, medical treatment centres, and rehabilitation centres for local and foreign tourists to improve and restore their health is evidence of the state’s support for the development of the tourism industry in our country. It is worth noting that effective work is being done by representatives of the field to develop medical infrastructure and services in Uzbekistan. Due to the development of healthcare institutions, the country has the opportunity to develop medical tourism. Specialised clinics and health resorts contribute more to the development of medical tourism.

Currently, more than 100 sanatoriums and children’s camps are operating in our country. Operating sanatoriums accept vacationers according to their speciality. They differ in their speciality, treatment methods, and services they offer. (Table 1)

Table 1: Types of sanatoriums according to specialisation. Author’s development based on Internet data

Balneological	Treatment with mineral waters. Patients take various baths, and procedures and drink mineral water. Such sanatoriums are usually located near mineral water sources.
Mud therapy	The main focus here is mud treatment. Peloids (healing clay) are used in the form of wraps or baths.
Climatic	In such places, the unique features of the local climate are used: sea, mountain, and forest air. Staying in a certain climate zone can have a positive effect on the body.
Physiotherapy	They offer treatment using physical factors: ultrasound, laser, magnets, currents, etc
Prophylactic	These institutions are aimed at prevention of diseases, recovery from diseases and promotion of health.
Specialised	These are institutions aimed at the treatment of certain diseases or a group of diseases, for example, sanatoriums for the treatment of cardiovascular, respiratory, and musculoskeletal diseases, etc.
Children’s recreation centres	Specially adapted for the treatment and recreation of children. Here attention is paid not only to medical but also to entertainment and educational aspects.

The main goal of sanatorium-resort treatment is to improve the protective mechanism of the human body and prevent diseases - prevention, or the post-disease stage - the rehabilitation process.

In recent years, the demand of the population for the recreation type of tourism in Uzbekistan has been increasing. To study their needs and interests in recreation, a social survey was conducted among the citizens. 105 (50.5%) men and 103 (49.5%) women participated in the survey. The participants consisted of representatives of various fields, that is, teachers, doctors, students, entrepreneurs, retired people and other fields. To

find out which regions of the population rested in the sanatoriums, the % indicators were added to the question asked in the questionnaire:

Diagram 1: A social survey was conducted by the author on the topic “Prospects for the development of recreational tourism in Uzbekistan”.

According to the answers given by the survey participants, it can be seen that the demand for sanatoriums and recreation centres in the Tashkent region is much higher than others. Sanatoriums in the Fergana Valley have a low percentage in the survey, but they are in the leading positions in the list of the best sanatoriums in the republic. In addition, regions such as Tashkent and the Fergana Valley have a long tradition of sanatoriums and spas. The development of modern health facilities can attract local and international tourists who want relaxation and rehabilitation services after medical treatments. In the next places, the “Zomin” sanatorium of the Jizzakh region and the “Miraki” recreation centres of the Kashkadarya region are in high demand.

If we analyze the next diagram taking into account the age indicators of the survey participants, 67.5% of the respondents preferred to rest in entertainment centres organized on the mountain slopes. 19.2% of the participants said that they prefer to rest in sanatoriums. It can be seen from this that the activities of entertainment resorts organized in mountainous regions are well-established and in high demand.

Diagram 2: A social survey was conducted by the author on the topic “Prospects for the development of recreational tourism in Uzbekistan”.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Uzbekistan has a rich history of folk medicine, including herbal remedies. Integrating traditional medical practices with modern medical facilities can make the country a holistic healthcare destination.

Establishing rehabilitation centres focused on medical tourism can help people who want to recover after surgery or injuries in a peaceful environment.

To further improve the service quality of sanatoriums operating in Uzbekistan and to constantly advertise information about their activities in mass media and social networks.

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